

Impact Of Physical Activity and Screen Time On Occurrence Of Bruxism In Children - A Cross-Sectional Study

Research Article

Deepa Gurunathan^{1*}, Deeksheetha², Nivedhitha³, Joyson Moses⁴, Mahesh Ramakrishnan⁵

¹ Professor Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai - 600077, Tamilnadu, India.

² Graduate Student, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai - 600077, Tamilnadu, India.

³ Professor, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai - 600077, Tamilnadu, India.

⁴ Professor, Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, Thai Moogambigai Dental College and Hospital, Mogappair, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India.

⁵ Reader, Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai - 600077, Tamilnadu, India.

Abstract

Introduction: Bruxism is the habitual grinding, gnashing or clenching of teeth at times other than for the mastication of food. Bruxism is characterised by an involuntary sleep/awake parafunctional activity of the masticatory muscles, rhythmic or in spasm, and may present teeth clenching and/or grinding. The aim of this study is to evaluate the correlation between bruxism and physical activity.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted among 300 dyads of parents and children between ages 4 and 6 years of age. A questionnaire containing questions about time spent on physical activity and evaluating occurrence of bruxism.

Results: The total number of children who participated in this study were 300. 160(53.33%) were male children, while the rest 140(46.67%) were female children. 152(95%) male children exhibited various signs of bruxism, while only 70(50%) of the female children had signs of bruxism. This could be attributed to the fact that 95% of the male children spent more than 2 hours with their gadgets and only 30.7% of the female children spent more than 2 hours on their gadgets. Children who practiced more physical activity, were less prone to the bruxism. 91.7% of the male children got only less than 1 hour of physical activity, where as 68.5% of female children got more than 2 hours of physical activity. However, children who spent more time with gadgets were more prone to the bruxism, 80% of the male children spent more than 2 hours with their gadgets, while only 30.7% of the female children spent more than 2 hours with their gadgets.

Conclusion: On the basis of the data collected physical activities can reduce stress of daily stressful life. There is a mild association between the presence of parafunctional habits and the practice of physical activity in children of ages between 4 and 6 years of age. With the given limitations of the study it can be concluded that children who played more had reduced incidence of bruxism.

Keywords: Bruxism; Physical Activity; Gadget Usage; Temporomandibular Joint Disorder.

Introduction

Bruxism, is the habitual grinding, gnashing or clenching of teeth at times other than for the mastication of food, and was originally described by Marie and Pietkiewicz in 1907 [1]. The American

Academy of Orofacial pain defines bruxism as, diurnal or nocturnal parafunctional activity including clenching, bracing, gnashing, and grinding of the teeth [2]. Bruxism is characterised by an involuntary sleep/awake parafunctional activity of the masticatory muscles, rhythmic or in spasm, and may present teeth clenching

*Corresponding Author:

Deepa Gurunathan,
Professor, Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University,
Chennai - 600077, Tamilnadu, India.
Email Id: deepag@saveetha.com

Received: February 02, 2021

Accepted: February 28, 2021

Published: March 02, 2021

Citation: Deepa Gurunathan, Deeksheetha, Nivedhitha, Joyson Moses, Mahesh Ramakrishnan. Impact Of Physical Activity and Screen Time On Occurrence Of Bruxism In Children - A Cross-Sectional Study. *Int J Dentistry Oral Sci.* 2021;08(03):1832-1839. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19070/2377-8075-21000364>

Copyright: Deepa Gurunathan©2021. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

and/or grinding [3].

The condition has been variously attributed to dental, systemic or psychological factors. In most dental literature it is reported to be secondary to intraoral conditions such as malocclusion or localised conditions including mobile teeth, cuspal interferences, high restorations, premature contacts or occlusal disharmony [4]. The Systemic factors which are implicated in bruxism include intestinal parasites, subclinical nutritional deficiencies, allergies and endocrine disorders [5].

Physical activities can reduce stress in daily life. If not eliminated, stress is able to promote large increases in muscle tension, hypertension, asthma, heart arrhythmia and the development of parafunctions [6]. In this modern day, sedentary lifestyle has become more and more common, and has started to affect children more commonly, leading to diseases like diabetes due to excessive weight gain [7]. Children who lack interest in exercises or in games, children who don't have the time and money for exercises are in greater danger of developing parafunctional habits and other chronic illness than those who exercise regularly [8].

According to the American College of Sports Medicine, a good approach is to encourage children to try short periods of exercises with moderate intensity [9]. In relation to the type of activity, it is recommended any activity that uses major muscle groups in a continued, rhythmic and aerobic way (for example, walking, jogging, cycling) [10]. Children who belong to the lower economic statuses don't have access to platforms where in they can practice physical activity [11].

Studies including the correlation of physical activity with the beginning of parafunctional habits such as bruxism or even temporomandibular issue (TMD) are rare. This study aims at identifying the presence of parafunctional habits in children and confirm its possible association with the practice of physical activity.

Materials and Methods

Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Scientific review board of the university. The study was conducted among 300 dyads of parents and children between ages 4 and 6 years of age. A total of 160 boys and 140 girls took part in the study.

A questionnaire containing questions about time spent on physical activity was made along with another questionnaire evaluating bruxism and other parafunctional habits. The questionnaire was planned by multiple examiners and was given to the parents. Along with it, clinical oral examination of the children was done using icecream sticks. The presence of temporomandibular joint clicking noises were observed by the tactile method. An informed consent was obtained from the children and the children's parents who had participated in the study.

Children with the following conditions were not included in the study:

Changes in cognitive functions.

Children with large carious lesion.

Impaired communication skills.

History of recent trauma to the face.

If parental consent could not be obtained.

Evaluation of the parafunctional habits was conducted using a self-reporting questionnaire (yes/not) about the habits of nail biting, chewing gums with frequency, biting objects, biting lips/cheeks, and supporting the chin with the hand (adapted from the protocol proposed by K. Koyano et al [12]. The information on the practice of physical activity was gathered in accordance with the number of hours of exercise obtained by the child in a day.

I) Questionnaire

Questionnaire For Evaluating Bruxism:

Are you aware of or heard your child grind his/her teeth during sleep?

Yes

No

Have noticed your child's dentition is worn down?

Yes

No

Does your child complain of tightness or soreness of the jaws upon awakening ?

Yes

No

Does your child complain of aching temples upon awakening?

Yes

No

Does your child complain of difficulty in opening the mouth after waking up?

Yes

No

Have you heard or felt joint clicks in your child's jaws after he/she wakes up?

Yes

No

II) Clinical Examination

Abnormal wear of teeth-

Wear of enamel only.

Wear of enamel and dentin.

Wear up to 1/3rd of the length of the crown.

More than 1/3rd of the length of the crown.

Sounds associated with bruxism -

Present.

Absent.

Discomfort of the jaws-

Present.

Absent.

III) Evaluation Of Child's Physical Activity:

1. In your child's daily regime, time spent playing games

- A) half an hour to one.
- B) one to one and half.
- C) more than one and a half.

2. Does your child utilise your P.T periods well?

- A) yes
- B) no

3. What time does your child play?

- A) before school.
- B) after school.
- C) during school.
- D) both after and at school.

4. What type of physical activity does your child do?

- A) walking.
- B) running.
- C) bicycling.
- D) games.
- E) all of the above.

5. Is your child really interested in physical activity?

- A) yes
- B) no

6. When do you entertain yourself?

- A) before school.
- B) after school.
- C) both.

7. Your child entertains himself/herself with _____

- A) TV.
- B) Mobiles, tablets and laptops.
- C) gaming stations.
- D) two and more from above.

8. Time spent on entertainment activities by your child

- A) less than half an hour.
- B) half an hour to one hour.
- C) more than one hour.

9. Time spent studying at home

- A) half an hour.
- B) one hour.
- C) more than one.

10. What is your child's academic performance?

- A) below 35.
- B) 35-50.
- C) 50 -75.
- D) 75 and above.

Statistical Analysis:

The values and variables were tabulated and analysed using the SPSS software by IBM. Chi square tests were done to assess the correlation and association. Any p value of less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant. The independent variables were age and gender, while the dependent variables were timing of gadget usage, time spent of physical activity, signs of teeth wear, difficulty in mouth opening and sounds associated with bruxism.

Results

The results obtained from the study are given in the graphs and table below. (Graph 1) shows the gender distribution of the children who had participated in this study. 160 (53.33%) were male children and the rest 140 (46.67%) were female children. (Graph 2) shows the total time spent on physical activity by the children. Only 104 (34.67%) of the children spent more than 2 hours on physical activity, while 31 (10.33%) of children spent 1-2 hours on physical activity, while a majority 165 (55%) of the children spent less than 1 hour playing. A majority 195 (65%) of the children used their gadgets for more than 2 hours. 61 (20.33%) of the children spent 1-2 hours on their gadgets. (Graph 3). Tooth wear was seen in most of the children, 45.33% of the children had wear of only enamel, while 26% of the children showed no signs of tooth wear. (Graph 4) All children 195(65%) who spent more than 2 hours on their gadgets presented with signs of bruxism. All children 44(14.67%) who spent less than 1 hour on their gadgets had no signs of bruxism. (Graph 5) 80% of the male children spent more than 2 hours with their gadgets, while only

Graph 1. This graph shows the gender distribution of the children who had participated in this study.

30.7% of the female children spent more than 2 hours with their gadgets. (Graph 6) 91.7% of the male children got only less than 1 hour of physical activity, where as 68.5% of female children got more than 2 hours of physical activity. (Graph 7) 77(74%) of the children who spent more than 2 hours on physical activity had no signs of bruxism. 54(33.7%) of the children who spent less than 1 hour on physical activity had wear of more than 1/3 rd of the teeth structure. (Graph 8) 36(22.5%) of the male children had more than 1/3rd of tooth wear, and 18(12.8%) of the female children had more than 1/3rd of tooth wear. (Graph 9) When clicking sounds in the TMJ were heard after waking up, it was found that 54(64%) of the children had more than 1/3 rd of tooth wear, while the rest 30(36%) wear of both enamel and dentin. No clicking sounds was heard on waking up when there was only enamel wear or when there was no signs of wear present. (Graph 10) In children who complained of difficulty in mouth opening after waking up it was found that 54(60%) of the children had wear

of more than 1/3rd of tooth structure. 32(35%) had wear of enamel and dentin. (Graph 11) 95(31.67%) of the parents did not notice worn down dentition in children with wear of only enamel (Graph 12) 54(75%) had wear of more than 1/3rd of tooth structure when of parents heard grinding of teeth at night, and 136(64.5%) did not hear grinding of teeth at night when only signs of enamel wear were present (Graph 13).

Discussion

Previously our team has conducted numerous original studies [13-26] over the past 6 years. The idea for this present study stemmed due to current interest in our community. Physical activity reduces the stress that aggravates psychophysical problems, our hypothesis was that physically less active children could present more parafunctions and extra facial pain [27].

Graph 2. This graph shows the total time spent on physical activity by the children.

Graph 3. This graph shows the total time spent by children using gadgets. A majority 195 (65%) of the children used their gadgets for more than 2 hours. 61 (20.33%) of the children spent 1-2 hours on their gadgets. And 44(14.67%) of the students spent less than 1 hour on their gadgets.

Graph 4. This graph represents the amount of tooth wear seen in the children of the study population. 18% of the children had more than 1/3rd of tooth wear, 10.67% of the children had wear of both enamel and dentin, 45.33% of the children had wear of only enamel, while 26% of the children showed no signs of tooth wear.

In this study male and female children between the ages of 4 and 6 were considered, male children were more affected by bruxism than female children, which was similar to the results obtained by Sruthi S and Deepa G in their study; whose study population included male and female children from 6 to 12 years of age [28].

In accordance to the results obtained in this study, the amount of time spent on physical activity by children has a significant association with the parafunctional habits such as bruxism, daytime clenching, and extra facial pain. Children who practiced more physical activity, were less prone to bruxism. However, children who spent more time with gadgets such as the television, video

games etc, were more prone to the parafunctional habits such as bruxism, daytime clenching and showed considerable wear of teeth and joint clicks than those who spent lesser time with gadgets. According to the study conducted by, Bonafe et al, 28% felt that they could feel or have heard their child's joint click, which was similar to the study conducted 30% of the children had difficulty in mouth opening after waking up, while the studies conducted by Bonafe et al, showed about 36% [29].

Clinical examination of the children's teeth was done by looking the incisors, 50% of the children had some form of teeth wear, while in the study by Carolina Bortoletto et al, 37% of the

Graph 5. This graph shows the association between signs of bruxism and the timing of gadget use. The children who had more than 2 hours of physical activity showed significantly less signs of bruxism than children who had less than 1 hour of physical activity. The chi square test revealed significant results. p value = 0.000 which is less than 0.005.

Graph 6. This graph shows the association between gender and the timing of gadget use. There was a significant difference in the timing of gadget usage between male and female children. P value =0.000, p value lesser than 0.005, 80% of the male children spent more than 2 hours with their gadgets, while only 30.7% of the female children spent more than 2 hours with their gadgets.

Graph 7. This graph shows the association between gender and time spent on physical activity. There was a significant difference in the time spent on physical activity between male and female children. P value =0.000, p<0.005, 91.7% of the male children got only less than 1 hour of physical activity, whereas 68.5% of female children got more than 2 hours of physical activity.

children grind their teeth showed about 40% of the children had nighttime teeth grinding and daytime clenching [30]. Winocur E et al, amongst Israeli adolescents showed that only 20% of the students had sleep bruxism. 28% of the children had clicking sounds in their TMJ which was similar to the results obtained in this study [31].

Children with sleep bruxism may have additional symptoms during the day, such as headaches, earaches, and pain in the mastication muscles. According to Carra et al, sleep bruxism in young children can be associated with muscle fatigue, insomnia, noisy breathing during sleep, and headaches. 15% of the children who participated in this study had discomfort of the jaws, it was relatively higher about 25% in similar studies conducted by Carra et al [32].

According to the International Classification of Sleep Disorders (ICSD-3), using criteria proposed by the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM), Bruxism belongs to the group of movement disorders present in parasomnias [33]. The aetiology of

bruxism is complex and multifactorial, involving systemic, psychological, occupational, and genetic factors. However, the primary pathogenesis is related to the central nervous system (CNS) activities. Evidence suggests that SB occurs in response to excessive micro disturbances and is also related to the patient's quality of sleep. Emotional factors, such as anxiety, seem to be associated with Bruxism. Bruxism is often seen in children and adolescents, with a prevalence of 3.5% and 40.6% [34]. And bruxism can be seen in 13% of adults [35].

50% of the children played for more than one and half an hour after school everyday, 45% of the children played for one and less than one hour everyday after school, while only 5% of the children played for only half an hour free school. According to the study done by Taveras et al, children who played for more than 300 hours per week were about 60% [36]. The most common physical activity done by children participating in this study was running which was 37%, bicycling was 10%, games were 28% and children who liked running, bicycling and games were 24%. In a meta analysis conducted by Bruijns BA et al, it was found

Graph 8. This graph shows the association between signs of bruxism and the total hours spent on physical activity. The chi square test revealed significant results p value = 0.000 which is less than 0.005.

Graph 9. This graph shows the association between signs of bruxism and gender. The signs of bruxism were more pronounced in male children than the female children. But, the majority of the female children showed no signs of bruxism, while a majority of the male children showed signs of enamel wear.

Graph 10. This graph shows the association between signs of teeth wear and clicking sounds of the jaws noticed by the parents. The children's parents noticed clicking sounds in the children's joints after waking up signs when there was more than 1/3rd of teeth wear. While no clicking joints sounds were observed when only enamel wear was present, and no signs of teeth wear were seen. The chi square test revealed significant results p value = 0.000 which is less than 0.005.

Graph 11. This graph shows the association between signs of teeth wear and difficulty in mouth opening after waking up in the morning. The children’s parents noticed that their children had difficulty in mouth opening in the morning after waking up when there was more than rd of teeth wear. While no difficulty in mouth opening was observed when only enamel wear was present, and no signs of teeth wear were seen. The chi square test revealed significant results p value = 0.000 which is less than 0.005.

Graph 12. This graph shows the association between the worn down teeth noticed by the parents and wear of teeth noticed. The chi square test revealed significant results p value = 0.000 which is less than 0.005.

Graph 13. This graph shows the association between hearing of grinding of teeth at night noticed by the parents and wear of teeth noticed. The children’s parents heard grinding of teeth at night when there was more than 1/3rd of teeth wear, While no teeth grinding was heard at night by parents when only enamel wear was seen and no signs of teeth wear were seen. The chi square test revealed significant results p value = 0.000 which is less than 0.005.

that the average physical activity for toddlers should be about 3 hours a day [37].

Time spent using gadgets, such as mobiles, Laptops, playstations, TVs was more than 2 hours in 65% of the children, 1 to 2 hours was 15%, less than 1 hour was 20%. In the study by Hosakava Rikuya et al, only 14% of the children used mobile phones for more than one hour, while the rest 86% of the children used their mobile phones for less than one hour [38].

Since physical activity reduces the stress that aggravates psycho-physical problems, our hypothesis was that physically less active children could present more parafunctions and extra facial pain. Since bruxism/clenching have a multifactorial origin, they must be analysed with caution because many factors can trigger the onset and not only the absence of physical activity. Practice of

physical activity is of paramount importance especially in young children, as it helps in preventing other commonly occurring conditions like obesity and juvenile diabetes.

Conclusion

On the basis of the data collected physical activities can reduce stress of daily life. There is a mild association between the presence of parafunctional habits and the practice of physical activity in children of ages between 4 and 8 years of age. Children who played more had reduced incidence of bruxism. Although both genders showed a medium level of physical activity, the boys were more active than the girls since they devoted more hours of physical activity, during more days of the week, and this difference is statistically significant. Children who spent more time with their gadgets were more prone to bruxism, than children who

spent less time on their gadgets. With its limitations, further well planned clinical trials are essential to give a solid conclusion and bring about correlation between bruxism and physical activity.

References

- [1]. Marie MM, Pietkiewicz M. La bruxomanie [Bruxism]. *Revue Stomatol* 1907; 14: 107–116. Pubmed PMID: 20239159.
- [2]. American Academy of Orofacial Pain. Orofacial Pain: Guidelines for Assessment, Diagnosis, and Management. Quintessence Publishing Company, Incorporated, 2018.
- [3]. Restrepo CC, Vásquez LM, Alvarez M, et al. Personality traits and temporomandibular disorders in a group of children with bruxing behaviour. *J Oral Rehabil* 2008; 35: 585–593.
- [4]. Navarro G, Baradel AF, Baldini LC, et al. Parafunctional habits and its association with the level of physical activity in adolescents. *BrJP* 2018; 1: 46–50.
- [5]. Nunes AM, Martinez EM, Lopes PRR, Bittencourt MAV, de Moraes Cane-do PM, et al. Associação entre flexibilidade da cadeia muscular posterior e severidade de disfunção temporomandibular. *Revista de Ciências Médicas e Biológicas* 2016; 14: 394.
- [6]. Stults-Kolehmainen MA, Sinha R. The effects of stress on physical activity and exercise. *Sports Med* 2014; 44: 81–121.
- [7]. Sahoo K, Sahoo B, Choudhury AK, Sofi NY, Kumar R, Bhadoria AS. Childhood obesity: Causes and consequences. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care* 2015; 4: 187.
- [8]. West SL, Banks L, Schneiderman JE, Caterini JE, Stephens S, White G, et al. Physical activity for children with chronic disease; a narrative review and practical applications. *BMC Pediatr*. 2019 Jan 8;19(1):12. Pubmed PMID: 30621667.
- [9]. American College of Sports Medicine. ACSM's Guidelines for Exercise Testing and Prescription. 2000.
- [10]. Organization WH, Others. Young people's health—a challenge for society. (Report of a WHO Study Group on Young People and Health for All by the Year 2000, Technical Report Series 731). Geneva, Switzerland.
- [11]. Tanaka H, Terashima S, Borres MP, Thulesius O. Psychosomatic problems and countermeasures in Japanese children and adolescents. *Biopsychosoc Med*. 2012 Mar 20;6:6. Pubmed PMID: 22433184.
- [12]. Koyano K, Tsukiyama Y, Ichiki R, Kuwata T. Assessment of bruxism in the clinic. *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation* 2008; 35: 495–508.
- [13]. Jeevanandan G. Kedo-S Paediatric Rotary Files for Root Canal Preparation in Primary Teeth – Case Report. *JOURNAL OF CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC RESEARCH*.
- [14]. Govindaraju L, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian EMG. Comparison of quality of obturation and instrumentation time using hand files and two rotary file systems in primary molars: A single-blinded randomized controlled trial. *European Journal of Dentistry* 2017; 11: 376–379.
- [15]. Govindaraju L, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian EMG. Knowledge and practice of rotary instrumentation in primary teeth among Indian dentists: A questionnaire survey. *Journal of International Oral Health* 2017; 9: 45.
- [16]. Somasundaram S, Ravi K, Rajapandian K, Gurunathan D. Fluoride content of bottled drinking water in Chennai, Tamilnadu. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR*. 2015 Oct;9(10):ZC32.
- [17]. Jeevanandan G, Govindaraju L. Clinical comparison of Kedo-S paediatric rotary files vs manual instrumentation for root canal preparation in primary molars: a double blinded randomised clinical trial. *European Archives of Paediatric Dentistry*. 2018 Aug;19(4):273-8.
- [18]. Govindaraju L, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian EM. Clinical evaluation of quality of obturation and instrumentation time using two modified rotary file systems with manual instrumentation in primary teeth. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR*. 2017 Sep;11(9):ZC55.
- [19]. Ravikumar D, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian EMG. Evaluation of knowledge among general dentists in treatment of traumatic injuries in primary teeth: A cross-sectional questionnaire study. *Eur J Dent* 2017; 11: 232–237.
- [20]. Panchal V, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian EMG. Comparison of instrumentation time and obturation quality between hand K-file, H-files, and rotary Kedo-S in root canal treatment of primary teeth: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry* 2019; 37: 75.
- [21]. Packiri S, Gurunathan D, Selvarasu K. Management of Paediatric Oral Rana-ula: A Systematic Review. *J Clin Diagn Res* 2017; 11: ZE06–ZE09.
- [22]. Gurunathan D, Shanmugaavel AK. Dental neglect among children in Chennai. *J Indian Soc Pedod Prev Dent* 2016; 34: 364–369.
- [23]. Govindaraju L, Gurunathan D. Effectiveness of Chewable Tooth Brush in Children-A Prospective Clinical Study. *J Clin Diagn Res* 2017; 11: ZC31–ZC34.
- [24]. Subramanyam D, Gurunathan D, Gaayathri R, et al. Comparative evaluation of salivary malondialdehyde levels as a marker of lipid peroxidation in early childhood caries. *Eur J Dent* 2018; 12: 67–70.
- [25]. Ramakrishnan M, Bhurki M. Fluoride, Fluoridated Toothpaste Efficacy And Its Safety In Children-Review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2018 Oct 1;10(04):109-14.
- [26]. Lakshmanan L, Mani G, Jeevanandan G, Ravindran V, Ganapathi SE. Assessing the quality of root canal filling and instrumentation time using kedo-s files, reciprocating files and k-files. *Brazilian Dental Science*. 2020 Jan 31;23(1):7-p.
- [27]. Nieman P. Psychosocial aspects of physical activity. *Paediatrics & child health*. 2002 May 1;7(5):309-12.
- [28]. Suguna S, Gurunathan D. Quality of life of children with sleep bruxism. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2020 Jan 28;9(1):332-336. Pubmed PMID: 32110614.
- [29]. Bonafé FSS. Fatores de risco para a disfunção temporomandibular em adolescentes: estudo caso-controle [Dissertação de Mestrado]. Araraquara: Faculdade de Odontologia da UNESP.
- [30]. Bortoletto CC, Salgueiro MDCC, Valio R, Fragoso YD, Motta PB, Motta LJ, et al. The relationship between bruxism, sleep quality, and headaches in schoolchildren. *J Phys Ther Sci*. 2017 Nov;29(11):1889-1892. Pubmed PMID: 29200617.
- [31]. Winocur E, Messer T, Eli I, Emodi-Perlan A, Kedem R, Reiter S, et al. Awake and Sleep Bruxism Among Israeli Adolescents. *Front Neurol*. 2019 Apr 26;10:443. Pubmed PMID: 31105645.
- [32]. Carra MC, Huynh N, Morton P, Rompré PH, Papadakis A, Remise C, et al. Prevalence and risk factors of sleep bruxism and wake-time tooth clenching in a 7- to 17-yr-old population. *Eur J Oral Sci*. 2011 Oct;119(5):386-94. Pubmed PMID: 21896056.
- [33]. American Academy of Sleep Medicine Guidelines.
- [34]. Manfredini D, Restrepo C, Diaz-Serrano K, Winocur E, Lobbezoo F. Prevalence of sleep bruxism in children: a systematic review of the literature. *Journal of oral rehabilitation*. 2013 Aug;40(8):631-42.
- [35]. Yap AU, Chua AP. Sleep bruxism: Current knowledge and contemporary management. *J Conserv Dent*. 2016 Sep-Oct;19(5):383-9. Pubmed PMID: 27656052.
- [36]. Taveras EM, Field AE, Berkey CS, Rifas-Shiman SL, Frazier AL, Colditz GA, et al. Longitudinal relationship between television viewing and leisure-time physical activity during adolescence. *Pediatrics*. 2007 Feb;119(2):e314-9. Pubmed PMID: 17272594.
- [37]. Bruijns BA, Truelove S, Johnson AM, Gilliland J, Tucker P. Infants' and toddlers' physical activity and sedentary time as measured by accelerometry: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2020 Feb 7;17(1):14. Pubmed PMID: 32028975.
- [38]. Hosokawa R, Katsura T. Association between mobile technology use and child adjustment in early elementary school age. *PLoS One*. 2018 Jul 25;13(7):e0199959. Pubmed PMID: 30044819.